

COMPOSITE HEAT TRANSFER MATERIALS FOR ELECTRONIC
PACKAGING IN FUTURE DOD SYSTEMS

W. C. Riley
Research Opportunities, Inc.
P.O. Box 7000-303
Palos Verdes Peninsula, CA 90274

and

M. A. Kinna
Office of Naval Technology
800 No. Quincy Street
Arlington, VA 22217-5000

ABSTRACT

Department of Defense weapon and platform systems for the 1990s require improved methods for thermal management in electronics, with emphasis on increased thermal conductivity and appropriate thermal expansion matching between adjacent components. High thermal conductivity (Hi-K) graphite fibers can be combined unidirectionally with organic, metal, carbon, and ceramic matrices to maximize the thermal conductivity of electronic package thermal planes. When thermal expansion matching is required, cross-ply designs can be constructed with aluminum or copper matrices to achieve high fiber volume loading; K values of graphite-aluminum have been measured that are three times that of copper-Invar-copper (CIC) at about one-third the density. Hi-K fibers can also be used in organic matrix composites to provide a minimum weight, minimum volume composite to serve as the constraining core for a glass epoxy printed wiring board (PWB). When isotropic thermal conductivity combined with thermal expansion control is required, as in a chip carrier component, artificial diamond particulate reinforcement can be used. Successful property translation has been demonstrated in an aluminum matrix. Additional studies will be conducted for dielectric matrices such as AlN. Data supporting the area of composites in the applications discussed above will be presented.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Thermal Conductivity; Electronic Packaging; Thermal Expansion Control; Thermal Management in Electronic Devices.

1. INTRODUCTION

As power requirements for electronic devices increase and the module size decreases, heat dissipation techniques must be improved significantly. In addition, the stresses between components that result from increased thermal flow can lead to thermal stress failures during thermal cycling due to mismatched thermal expansion in adjacent components. These problems will become limiting in future electronic devices used by DOD. A possible solution is the use of composite materials with high thermal conductivity reinforcements for lightweight, efficient thermal conduction. Also, the selection of composite architecture with low or negative thermal expansion reinforcements can be used to tailor the thermal expansion of individual components.

To date, a number of composite materials systems have been examined for potential use in devices. In particular, near-term applications have been found for discontinuous silicon carbide reinforced aluminum which maintains the thermal conductivity of unreinforced aluminum while significantly decreasing the thermal expansion to a point where it is advantageous for current devices. In particular, the lower density and higher thermal conductivity of the composite relative to CIC or Kovar, which are normally used for thermal expansion control, make this composite attractive. However, it is the purpose of this paper to reach beyond the thermal management capability of discontinuous silicon carbide aluminum and assess the potential of more advanced composite materials for such applications as module frames and printed wiring board constraining cores.

The recent stimulation of interest in advanced composite concepts has been motivated primarily by the development of high thermal conductivity pitch based graphite fibers with thermal conductivity in the range of 1100 W/mK (almost three times that of copper), a negative coefficient of thermal expansion (-1.6 ppm/°C) and an exceedingly high modulus (896 - 965 GPa). Also, the development of high thermal conductivity, low density and low thermal expansion particulate materials such as artificial diamond and cubic boron nitride has been exciting. While the advanced particulates have great potential for future development, there is almost no data on composites containing these reinforcements. Therefore, this paper emphasizes the use of the pitch based graphite fibers, although there will be important applications indicated for the advanced particulate reinforced composites.

Since 1983, the Navy has been pioneering the development of high thermal conductivity carbon fibers that have high tensile modulus and a negative coefficient of thermal expansion in the fiber direction. The use of these fibers in composite materials can provide a tailored thermal expansion combined with exceedingly high thermal conductivity. A brief description of the fibers is presented below:

2. DISCUSSION OF FIBERS

The microstructure of these fibers approaches that of a single crystal of graphite and thus the properties are anisotropic with the extreme thermal conductivity only along the length of the fiber. This is indicated in Figure 1 which shows the crystal structure of graphite with strong covalent bonding in the two "a" directions providing the high thermal conductivity. The hexagonal crystal is held together in the third direction ("c" direction) only by van der Waals forces. In this direction, the thermal conductivity is virtually zero. Another critical aspect of thermal management is the thermal expansion. As would be expected, in the "c" direction of the graphite crystallite, there is extremely high thermal expansion and this causes a negative thermal expansion in the "a" directions. It is this contraction along the length of the fiber that permits a tailored thermal expansion in the composite by balancing the negative thermal expansion of the fiber with the positive thermal expansion of the matrix. The "c" direction is characterized by poor mechanical properties while the "a" directions show extremely high tensile strength and modulus.

Figure 2 shows the fiber thermal conductivity at room temperature as compared with other materials. The notation "P" indicates pitch precursor and the number indicates the fiber modulus in msi. These are designations of Amoco Performance Products. As noted above, the advanced pitch fiber (P130X) has a thermal conductivity almost three times that of copper which results in a specific thermal conductivity 12 times that of copper. Moreover, it is estimated that that ultimate thermal conductivity of the graphite fiber is in the neighborhood of 2400 W/mK. The thermal conductivity of even the most advanced fiber today is less than one-half of that value. The relationship between modulus and thermal expansion in graphite fibers is shown in Figure 3. Note that the thermal expansion saturates and becomes that of the graphite single crystal at a modulus of approximately 758 GPa. However, the continued increase in modulus with increasing thermal conductivity is significant in determining composite thermal expansion. Modulus saturation is expected in the range of 965 GPa. At that level, a thermal conductivity of approximately 800 W/mK would be expected. (See Figure 4). Further increases in thermal conductivity such as that shown for P130X can be achieved through crystal growth, a factor that does not affect modulus. Research projects at Amoco are expected to increase fiber thermal conductivity beyond the 1100 W/mK level.

3. ELECTRONIC PACKAGING REQUIREMENTS

The unique combination of thermal and physical properties of the pitch-based graphite fibers leads to numerous application possibilities for improved thermal management in electronic devices. As an example of the potential for use of composites, the SEM E thermal plane (also known as the module frame or heat sink) was chosen. The SEM E configuration is shown in Figure 5. The heat generated by

the chip is transmitted through the chip carrier and the PWB to the thermal plane and is then moved to the card rail and on to the air or water coolant. The requirements for the composite thermal plane were established by the Naval Weapon Support Center (NWSC) in Crane, Indiana. They include a thermal conductivity requirement of 220 W/mK with a goal of 300 W/mK in the direction of heat flow. In addition, there is a thermal expansion requirement of 5.0 to 9.0 ppm/°C. The density requirement is less than or equal to that of aluminum (2.71 grams/cc). Thus, the basic requirement was for a material that would exceed the heat transfer capacity of aluminum while reducing the thermal expansion into the range of the PWB. Note that there are many other important requirements such as torsion, environmental stability and damping. These are discussed in the accompanying paper by Kevin Beasley of NWSC.

4. COMPOSITE DESIGN

The combined thermal expansion and thermal conductivity requirements cannot be met with any single material. The range of available materials is shown in Figure 6 where planar isotropic thermal expansion is shown in relation to the thermal conductivity. In order to meet the indicated SEM E goals, it is necessary to combine the high and low thermal expansion materials and to maintain high thermal conductivity. The density requirement precludes the traditional use of the CIC sandwich structure commonly used to control thermal expansion.

Several combinations of reinforcements and matrices were examined to determine their potential. This was an analytical examination using the CLASS program developed by Material Sciences Corporation. The most likely combinations were the high thermal conductivity graphite fibers in aluminum, copper and organic matrices. Note that the graphite copper (Gr/Cu) will not meet the density requirement; however, this composite is of interest for applications that are volume limited rather than weight limited. Figure 7 shows thermal conductivity and thermal expansion of these composites. Volume fraction increases as thermal expansion decreases. It is the higher modulus of the metal relative to the organic that provides the higher thermal expansion at a given volume fraction. The organic matrix composites clearly do not meet the thermal expansion criteria at the level of thermal conductivity that is needed. This is not to say that the organic composites have no role as thermal planes, it merely means that other methods must be taken to increase thermal expansion without decreasing thermal conductivity. An obvious answer would be to add aluminum into the composite; studies of that nature appear to have potential, but the metal matrix composites have received the most emphasis to date. Note from the figure that the goals are barely met by P130X/Al. The calculated curves are based on 1100 W/mK fiber and, as previously noted, higher fiber conductivity, and thus higher composite conductivity, can be expected in the near future.

Magnesium was also investigated as a matrix. From analytical studies, it appeared that the higher modulus of aluminum relative to magnesium would permit a greater volume fraction of fiber before reaching the lower limit of the thermal expansion requirement. This proved to be the case by experiment as well as modeling, and magnesium was dropped from the study. In Figure 8, the thermal expansion and thermal conductivity of fabricated Al and Mg matrix composites are shown. Note the lower thermal conductivity in the Mg composites for comparable thermal expansion. The goal shown here is substantially lower than SEM E, but is suitable for many applications.

Because of cost and some difficulty in machining the diamond-aluminum composite, very little data have been derived. However, a 25 volume fraction composite was made using Type 1B artificial diamond. Results indicated an excellent translation of diamond thermal conductivity into the composite. SiC/Al discontinuous composite closely reproduces the calculated relationship between volume fraction and thermal expansion. Diamond would be expected to give a similar result. A calculated thermal conductivity based on the same rule-of-mixtures translation found in the 25 volume fraction material indicates that at 55 volume fraction a thermal conductivity 300 W/mK might be attained. A great deal of additional work will be required to assess the potential of the diamond-aluminum composite.

5. EXPERIMENTAL DATA USING P130X FIBERS

Studies were conducted on the properties of copper and aluminum matrix composites reinforced with P130X fibers. The results were as predicted from other graphite-metal composite studies. The thermal expansion translation is close to prediction when sound composites are made, but the thermal conductivity translation is somewhat more variable. Figure 9 shows the data points in comparison with the model for property prediction. From this work, it is clear that the high thermal conductivity graphite fibers can be used in an aluminum matrix to satisfy the thermal expansion, thermal conductivity and density goals of NWSC. Gr/Cu will be the better performer in volume-limited applications.

The thickness direction ("Z") thermal conductivity of Gr/Al and Gr/Cu is substantially below predicted values, averaging 50-70% of that predicted by the model. However, in general, the PWB will be mounted on both sides of the thermal plane. A cross-ply graphite fiber composite can have the fibers in the direction of heat transfer closest to the printed wiring board with the cross-ply fibers at the center. This will minimize the penalty in the graphite fiber composite due to the low radial conductivity of the fiber. However, the isotropic thermal conductivity of diamond-aluminum would be an advantage.

For the electronic packaging application, thermal cycling is from -55°C to +125°C. Selected samples were tested for thermal and mechanical properties before and

after 500 cycles between these temperatures. The results in Tables 1 and 2 indicate no significant property change within the accuracy of the measurements. Higher thermal conductivity aluminum matrix composites are now being tested.

6. FUTURE CONSIDERATIONS FOR SEM E

While the major emphasis in this study was on the thermal plane, the potential for a broader use of composites in SEM E was examined. As indicated above, the reliability of high power devices will be impacted by the thermal expansion match between the various components of the device. This includes the chip carrier, PWB, and the thermal plane. (See Figure 5.) An attempt was made to show that a thermal expansion match to the silicon chip (3.2 ppm/°C) can be obtained in each of the components mentioned above. In this study, once the thermal expansion criteria for each component was satisfied, attention was given to thermal conductivity. A high thermal conductivity throughout the device is clearly desirable, however, in some cases this must be traded off against a precise thermal expansion match.

Chip Carrier The selection of material for the chip carrier is dominated by the requirement for dielectric properties. If dielectric properties are a strong requirement then aluminum nitride meets the general criteria very nicely. It has only a slightly higher thermal expansion than silicon and it has an excellent thermal conductivity, about 200 W/mK in pure material. Potentially, some benefits might be gained by the addition of diamond powder to the aluminum nitride. This should have an affect of slightly reducing the thermal expansion while increasing the thermal conductivity. However, there has been no demonstration of such a system.

Printed Wiring Board (PWB) Currently, the favorite material for the dielectric component of the PWB is E-glass-epoxy although various combinations of glass and organics have been used. Commonly, the requirement for thermal expansion in the printed wiring board is met by reducing the thermal expansion of glass epoxy with a CIC constraining core. For DOD, this is an unfortunate selection of materials because of the high density and the only moderate constraining ability of that composite. CIC cannot constrain glass-epoxy to the thermal expansion of silicon. The use of the high modulus high thermal conductivity carbon fibers appeared promising for the constraint. Core constraint depends on the product of the thermal expansion and the modulus. The high modulus combined with negative thermal expansion makes P130X-epoxy an ideal material for this application. Potentially, this composite would provide a minimum thickness of the constraining core as well as extremely low density. In addition, the high thermal conductivity of these fibers will provide much needed heat spreading throughout the PWB.

Using the thermal expansion of Al₂O₃ (frequently used as a chip carrier) as a goal, the potential performance comparison between Gr/Ep and CIC was calculated. Both minimum weight and minimum volume are strong requirements. The result of this study shows that the use of the P130X fiber in epoxy would reduce the

thickness of the constraining core by a factor of 4. When this factor is combined with the density difference, there could be a factor of 18 reduction in weight of the constraining core in going from CIC to Gr/Ep.

The primary uncertainty with Gr/Ep is the possibility of shear failure under thermal cycling. This results from the thermal expansion mismatch between the Gr/Ep and the Gl/Ep which is augmented by the difference in modulus. The thermal cycling behavior has yet to be evaluated, however, the maximum stress induced may be a result of cooldown from fabrication temperature. The hybrid composites of glass-epoxy and P130X/epoxy made to date have survived the cooldown without any obvious deterioration. C-scan and X-ray show excellent bonding between the composites.

Thermal Plane As indicated above, considerable work has been done on the thermal plane and it appears that the graphite aluminum composite can be used readily to provide a combination of correct thermal expansion, maximum thermal conductivity, and minimum weight. To demonstrate the 3.2 ppm/°C goal, a composite architecture of 38 v/o P130X/6063 was utilized. A thermal conductivity of 330 W/mK and a thermal expansion of 3.0 ppm/°C were measured on composites that were full-size SEM E thermal planes. (See Figure 9.)

7. CONCLUSIONS

1. The thermal conductivity, thermal expansion and density goals for the SEM E thermal plane can be met through the development of composite materials. This was demonstrated in measurements on Gr/Al composite panels.
2. The use of metal matrix composites has a strong advantage in thermal conductivity over organic or carbon matrices because of 1) higher matrix thermal conductivity, and 2) higher matrix modulus which permits a higher volume percent of fiber before reaching the minimum allowable thermal expansion. This, in turn, provides higher composite thermal conductivity. Gr/Al is recommended for weight-limited applications and Gr/Cu for volume limited applications.
3. The potential payoff for substitution of high modulus graphite fiber reinforced organic matrix composites for CIC as constraining core for the SEM E PWB is a weight savings in the core that exceeds a factor of 10. Full demonstration of this concept is recommended.
4. Using composites, there is strong potential for creating a SEM E module with a thermal expansion match to the Si chip in the chip carrier, printed wiring board, and thermal plane. This would be expected to significantly increase reliability of high power devices.
5. Experimental data indicates that the model used for prediction of thermal and mechanical properties of composites for heat sink applications is generally

adequate. Measured thermal conductivity values averaged about 20% below calculated values. Aluminum matrix composites showed thermal expansion values that are close to the values predicted by the model.

6. Before advanced composites are used routinely in electronic devices, reproducibility of properties must be established, the data base enlarged and producibility on a production basis must be demonstrated.

Table 1. Longitudinal Mechanical Properties Before and After 500 Thermal Cycles from -55°C to 125°C

• ROOM TEMPERATURE VALUES

Panel	Tensile Strength, MPa		Tensile Modulus, GPa		
	Before	After	Before	After	Calculated
39 v/o P120/6063	267.5	304.1	166.2	172.4	186.2
58 v/o P120/Cu Alloy	194.4	199.2	171.0	201.3	274.4
44 v/o P130X/Pure Cu	273.0	275.8	165.5	142.7	226.1

Table 2. Longitudinal Thermal Properties Before and After 500 Thermal Cycles from 55°C to 125°C

• ROOM TEMPERATURE VALUES

Panel	Thermal Conductivity W/mK		Thermal Expansion ppm/°C	
	Before	After	Before	After
39 v/o P120/6063	218	203	4.1	5.2
58 v/o P120/Cu Alloy	259	292	3.2	3.1
44 v/o P130X/Pure Cu	284	322	2.7	2.7

Figure 1. Graphite Crystal Structure

Figure 2. Thermal Conductivity of Metals and Carbons

Figure 3. Longitudinal Thermal Expansion and Modulus of Graphite Fibers

Figure 4. Fiber Thermal Conductivity as a Function of Modulus

Figure 5. SEM E Component Configuration

Figure 6. Thermal Conductivity and Thermal Expansion of Selected Materials

Figure 7. Composite Thermal Conductivity versus Thermal Expansion for X-Ply P130X (1100 W/mK) in Selected Matrices

Figure 8. Thermal Conductivity and Thermal Expansion of Selected Materials

Figure 9. Composite Thermal Conductivity versus Thermal Expansion for X-Ply P130X (1100 W/mK) in Selected Matrices

Mr. William C. Riley has been engaged in development and evaluation of advanced metals, ceramics and composite materials for the past 30 years. Currently he is President of Research Opportunities, Inc., a small company dedicated to assisting DOD in the application of new materials to advanced systems. From 1961 to 1982, Mr. Riley was employed by The Aerospace Corporation and was a consultant to the Office of the Under Secretary of Defense for Research and Engineering. From 1968 to 1982, he was Director of the Aerospace Materials Sciences Laboratory. In that position, he and his staff were responsible for materials technology in satellite, launch vehicle and ballistic missile systems. Previously, he held technical management positions with Atomics International Division of Rockwell, Battelle Memorial Institute, and General Electric. Mr. Riley has a B.S. degree in Chemical Engineering from the University of Notre Dame and an M.S. in Mathematics from the University of Illinois.

Mr. Marlin Kinna is the Task Area Manager for the Navy's Exploratory Development Program on Materials. Advanced Materials are identified and developed for systems applications ranging from Navy spacecraft to deep diving submarines. Prior to his present position at the Office of Naval Technology, Mr. Kinna was the Materials Technology Administrator for the Surface Warfare Weapons and Combat Systems Directorate of the Naval Sea Systems Command. He has over 30 years of experience in development of new materials for advanced Navy weapons and platforms systems. Mr. Kinna has a B.S. degree in Chemical Engineering and an M.S. in Nuclear Engineering from the University of Maryland.

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